

Efficiency and cost containment in primary healthcare team-based practices

Authors: *Joana Pestana, Jonas Schreyögg, and Pedro Pita Barros*

ABSTRACT

Objectives: The development of team-based practice allows for improved capacity and access within a collaborative multidisciplinary environment. Studies to date have analysed the mean effect of the physician group consolidation. However, there is still limited evidence as to whether these practices are positively associated with higher efficiency and quality of health care when the scale of the practice increases. Using the concepts of technical and allocative efficiency, this study analyses the costs of family physician practices with different sizes and organizational models (team-based and non-team-based). We investigate the relationship between the team-based care model and the extensive margin of the practices both as a separate (additive) and a joint effect (interaction).

Methods: We estimate the stochastic frontiers using a one-step approach for panel data. The analysis is based on administrative data from 750 physician practices in Portugal for the years 2016 to 2018. Our main outcome measures are the health care professionals' activities (office and domestic visits, number of hours) and the costs (based on the fixed labour costs and variable costs from prescription costs and performance incentives). Two output scenarios were analysed. An "activity-oriented" scenario, using the volume of visits, and a "quality-oriented" one, based on quality of care indicators for patients with chronic conditions, child and maternal care. We included the shared practice resources and some contextual characteristics to control for the health care needs and access barriers of the population.

Results: We found no significant differences in the production frontier between organizational models. This suggests that the underlying "technology" to produce health care services is not different in the self-selected team-based practices and that the productivity differences observed could come from differences in the efficient use of clinical resources. When considering the sources of the extra costs that can explain the differences in the unitary costs between and within organizational models, we observe that the maturity of the team is contributing to a better technical efficiency but is associated with higher costs. The study of the cost frontiers highlights that the groups that self-selected into team-based practices, with and without performance incentives, are significantly associated with lower costs, after adjusting for their levels of quality of care and environmental factors. However, this effect does not dominate for all scales of practices, i.e. team-based groups are not uniformly better than other practices.